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**Mode-I fracture in plain-weave glass epoxy composites:
Fracture toughness, resistance curve and traction separation
relationships**

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Mode-I fracture in plain-weave glass epoxy composites: Fracture toughness, resistance curve and traction separation relationships

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Background: High Energy Low Velocity Impact

Large Impact Drop Tower "Tower of Power" at CCM,ATTL

The Problem: The baseline panel's lack of superior through-thickness stiffness and transverse shear strength result in easy initiation and spread of damage and limited resistance to further impact damage.

High Energy (Large mass) low velocity impact drop on thick section panel (ARL Program: MEDE)

Representative Unit Ceramic Tile Size: 4 in x 4 in Ceramic Tile

Thick-section Composite: Baseline Panel

- 44 layers of 24oz PW (5 tows x5 tows /sq-in) S-2 Glass with 463 sizing.
- Resin: SC15 Epoxy
- Laminate Thickness: 28.40 mm)
- Impact Energy : 7.4 kJ

Energy Dissipation Pathways in an LVI event

FIBER DAMAGE

- Fiber Failure (Tensile)
- Fiber Failure (Compressive)
- Fiber Crush

MATRIX DAMAGE

- In-plane Matrix Failure
- Matrix Cracks
- **Delamination**

INTERPHASE DAMAGE

- Fiber-Matrix Debonding

Delamination in Uni-Directional Composite, R. Olsson, 2012

Delamination in Woven Fabric Composites
 Christopher S. Meyer, 2022

Scope of this research:

- **Interlaminar Delamination** is the main energy absorbing mechanism and can be studied as a problem of fracture (separation of surfaces)
- The criteria for the initiation and propagation of delamination therefore becomes important to understand the mechanical response of the composite section.
- We first seek to understand this criteria in pure Mode-I (opening) loading which is the weakest deformation mode.
- While the focus is on Mode-I pure loading, we pursue an experimental approach followed by numerical modeling of the experiment utilizing the measured properties. This approach is being extended to other modes as well in ongoing collaborative work.

Objective #1: Fracture Toughness

ENERGY Approach: Strain Energy Release Rate \rightarrow Measure of Delamination Resistance (Fracture Toughness, G_I)

Pure Mode-I Fracture (Double Cantilever Beam) ASTM D 5528-21

Objective #2: Modeling Delamination (initiation and propagation)

Cohesive Zone Model

Cohesive Zone Models in FEA Environments such as LS-DYNA®, Abaqus

[Dugdale, Barenblatt, 1959/1960]

Image Ref: Alfredsson et al. 2015

Inputs to Cohesive Zone Model

Area under $\sigma - \delta$:

→ $LEFM (G_I) = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{\partial C_I}{\partial a}$

→ $J = \int_c^{ext} \left(W dy - T_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} dC \right)$

Strain Energy Release Rate calculated using the J-Integral (James R. Rice, 1968)

$$J_I = \frac{P \theta_p}{b}$$

Blackman et al. 2013

$$J = \frac{12(P'a)^2}{Eh^3} + P'(w'_1 - w'_2)$$

Hogberg et al. 2007

Experimental Setup using DIC

Plain Weave S-2
 Glass (5 tows x 5
 tows/sq.in) 24
 oz/yd² with 463
 sizing

RVE size: ~10 mm
 x 10mm

Optical Measurements using DIC (2D)-Dual FOV

FOV (Front): 10-12 um/pixel

1. Crack opening displacement (under 200 microns)
2. Root Rotation (calculated at the crack tip)

FOV (Behind): 50-70 um/pixel

1. Crack Length/propagation
2. Rotation of the adherends (under the load point)

Mode-I DCB (LEFM Analysis)

Classical Beam Theory is the basis for the LEFM approach.

The key assumptions:

1. DCB beams are considered as Euler Bernoulli beams
2. Beams have uniform thickness
3. Co-planar fracture (fracture initiates and propagates in the same plane) → typical of UD composites.
4. Rotations/slopes, deflections follow the small deformation assumption. Deformation in the adherends is linear elastic.
5. Beams are fixed cantilevers i.e. there is no rotation at the initial crack tip.

The Berry's method (based on the Experimental Compliance) has been accepted for use in data reduction per ASTM guidelines [Composites Design Encyclopedia]

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{\partial C_I}{\partial a} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

$$C = \frac{a^n}{H} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$G_I = \frac{n P_c \Delta_c}{2wa} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where n and H are parameters to be determined in Berry's method. P_c, Δ_c are the critical load and displacement in the fracture process

$$\text{Compliance (C)} = \frac{\text{Displacement } (\Delta)}{\text{Load (P)}}$$

where Δ_B is the compliance neglecting shear deformation

$$\Delta = \Delta_B \left(1 + \frac{3h^2 E}{40a^2 G_{13}} \right)$$

To minimize: $f_s = \frac{3h^2 E}{40a^2 G_{13}}$

For $f_s = 0.05$ (5%), the crack length **we must choose an initial crack length** that minimizes the effect of interlaminar shear deformation.

Beam Theory Formulations of the J-Integral

$$\theta_p = \theta_{When\ Fixed} + \theta_{Root}$$

$$J_I = \frac{P\theta_p}{b}$$

$$\theta_{When\ Fixed} = \frac{PL^2}{2EI} = \frac{6Pa^2}{Ebh^3}$$

$$J = \frac{12(P'a)^2}{Eh^3} + P'(w'_1 - w'_2)$$

where $(w'_1 - w'_2)$ is the relative rotation at the root tip

$$P' = \frac{P}{b}$$

Idealized Mesostructure of the Plain Weave Glass Epoxy Section

Some of the challenges with fabric type reinforcement is adherence to the LEFM assumptions. The fracture mechanisms are complicated by:

- Undulating Crack path along the PW architecture (not in the mid-plane).
- Crack meandering and jumping (by more than one tow height) due to lack of clear pathway (nesting)
- Secondary crack formation (within the tows)- surface energy (additional)

Irwin- Kies Equation

$$G_I = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{\partial C_I}{\partial a}$$

$$\text{Compliance } (C_I) = \frac{\text{Displacement } (\Delta)}{\text{Load } (P)}$$

$$C_I = \frac{2a^3}{3EI}$$

$$\Delta I = \frac{b(\delta h)^3}{12}$$

Using a thicker section to assess the influence of undulating crack propagation on the Mode-I Fracture Toughness

Mode-I DCB for RDL RDC (Thick Section)

- ❑ Reinforcement: 24 oz/yd² Plain Weave (5 tows x 5 tows/sq.in) with 463 sizing
- ❑ Resin system: RDL-RDC (Epoxy resin system with superior temperature resistance compared to SC-15 epoxy)
- ❑ Section type: Thick-section
- ❑ Number of Specimens : 3
- ❑ Total Thickness (Two Half beams): 10.08 (average)
- ❑ Width: 25.3 mm (average)
- ❑ Initial Crack Length: 47.26 mm
- ❑ Load Introduction: HINGES

Cyclic Testing:

Each specimen was subjected to the following:

- Loading up to prescribed displacement (load line), x , mm
- Unload back to reference position (closed)
- Next cycle, RELOAD until new prescribed displacement, $x + K$, mm

Force-Load Line Displacement Data for RDL-RDC Thick section (SP-3)

Need for cyclic vs monotonic Testing

The purpose of cyclic testing was guided by some preceding tests conducted under monotonic loading that showed an increase in fracture toughness with crack growth (plots shown below).

It therefore becomes key to understand how the traction laws evolve along the R-curve response

With cyclic testing, the measurement of R-curve fracture toughness (as well as the crack tip measurements) needed for the development of traction laws as a function of crack length is possible.

Fracture Toughness(G and J): Cyclic Testing

Confirmation that the Plain Weave Glass Epoxy shows presence of Resistance Curve across all specimens tested i.e. Increase in Energy absorption as the crack lengths increase (Δa) \rightarrow **R – curve or J – curve (J – Integral Fracture Toughness)(T.L Anderson, Fracture Mechanics)**

Unit:
 1 MPa-mm=1000 J/m²

Crack Displacements & Rotations measured using DIC

$$\theta_p = \theta_{When\ Fixed} + \theta_{Root}$$

Using DIC measurement, plot above shows that there is rotation of the cross-section at the root (which is typically considered to be fixed in classical LFM methods)

Measuring CTOD:

$$\Delta v = v_2 - v_1 \text{ (DIC Marker Measurements)}$$

Traction Separation Law for Delamination Fracture

Traction-Separation relationship (TSL) is a material property input required to accurately predict the delamination size and energy absorbed in an impact event.

It should be experimentally determined (*analogous to the material characterization efforts of a bulk material such as stress-strain response, modulus etc.*)

- Differentiation of J_I with respect to Crack Tip Opening Displacement (CTOD) yields the Cohesive Traction.

$$\sigma = \frac{\partial J}{\partial \delta}$$

- Cohesive Traction (σ) vs CTOD is the Traction Separation Relationship that is input to the CZM in FEA.

Representative Plot: Not the actual Traction-Separation Law

DCB RDL-RDC (SP-1, SP-2, SP-3)

Ensemble view: All specimens show reasonably good repeatability

Experimentally Measured Traction Laws

Inputs to a Bi-Linear Cohesive Zone Model
 TSLs as a function of crack length (R-curve)

Key Result: The Traction law inputs have been generated as a function of crack length

Cohesive Zone Length (L_{CZ})

Peak Traction: 20.53 MPa
 Crack Opening Displacement (Elastic): **0.035mm ~35 μ m**
 Crack Opening Displacement (Propagation): **0.089 mm ~89 μ m**

During prescribed displacement loading in the DCB:

- ❖ As displacement increases, the crack tip is not moving— instead, stresses increase near the tip, up until the peak/critical traction value. This is considered to be the elastic limit (no damage zone).
- ❖ Upon continued loading, cohesive zone forms and grows in length as more region ahead of the crack tip enters the softening part of the traction-separation law. Initial crack tip has not changed yet.
- ❖ This zone continues to grow until the energy release rate matches the critical energy required for crack propagation (considered as the area under the cohesive law).
- ❖ Next, crack propagation occurs and the crack tip shifts. So up until the instance of crack propagation, the cohesive zone is growing, and this growth reaches a maximum right before propagation – i.e. maximum Cohesive zone length (L_{czmax})

Using the experimentally measured traction laws coupled with the DIC measurements of the deflection in the region ahead of the crack tip, (L_{czmax}) can be determined.

Cohesive Zone Lengths (Experimental Measurement)

Local Deflection Profile: Onset of crack propagation

The maximum Cohesive zone length ($L_{cz,max}$): 1.71 mm for this load cycle has been determined using DIC measurements and the experimentally measured traction laws.

This load cycle is considered in the initiation region of the R-curve. Same approach will be used for tracking CZ lengths of all other cycles (along the R-curve)

Modeling the DCB Experiment in FEA (LS-DYNA®)

Cohesive zone length($L_{cz_{max}}$): 1.71 mm (using experimentally measured traction laws) [based on a particular loading cycle in the initiation region]

- This estimate using DIC measurements and experimentally measured traction laws can provide guidance on the mesh density needed in FEA.
- A good rule of thumb is to have at least three elements in the cohesive region.
- Therefore, we start with a Mesh Dimension(along crack path): $l_e = \frac{1.71 \text{ mm}}{3}$

$l_e = 0.508 \text{ mm}$ considered here.

Next steps: Convergence of the deflection profile in the crack tip region will guide in-plane and through thickness mesh density

FE Model (DCB)
 Total Length: 152.4 mm
 Initial Crack Length: 47.244 mm
 Width: 25.4 mm
 Thickness: 10.08 mm (16 layers)
 Half Thickness: 5.04 mm
 Cohesive Element Thickness : 1um
 Solid Element: 8 Noded Hexahedral with efficient HG control

Bi-Linear Input (CZM) : MAT_138 (LS-DYNA®)

- G-(0.806 MPa-mm)
- Peak Traction: 20 MPa
- Considered high initial stiffness ($\delta_{elastic} = \frac{\delta_{critical}}{100}$)

Δ – Load Line Displacement

$$\Delta = \Delta v + a_0(w'_1 - w'_2) + \frac{8P(a_0)^3}{E_{fit}bh^3}$$

LEFM Term

Root Displacement $\sim \Delta v = v_2 - v_1$

This load line displacement Δ relationship as demonstrated in FEA helps determine modulus fit (E_{fit}) using the acquired data (crack tip displacement, slope) from the DCB experiment.

Comparing the J-Integral Expressions (using FEA)

Using FEA, we demonstrate the equivalence used determining fracture toughness, which essentially come from the slope/rotation relationship.

$$J_{I(\text{Load Point})} = \frac{P\theta_p}{b}$$

$$\theta_p = \theta_{\text{When Fixed}} + \theta_{\text{Root}}$$

$$\frac{P}{b}(\theta_p) = \frac{P}{b}(\theta_{\text{When Fixed}} + \theta_{\text{Root}}) = J_I$$

$$J_{I(\text{crack tip})} = \frac{12(Pa)^2}{E_{fit}b^2h^3} + \frac{P}{b}(w'_1 - w'_2)$$

This slope relationship (as demonstrated in FEA) can be used to objectively identifying the crack tip location in the case of plain weave (fabric) composites where it is challenging sometimes to visually identify the crack tip.

In essence, the total slope at the hinge must be equivalent to the sum of the fixed end slope ($\theta_{\text{When Fixed}}$) and the slope at the root (θ_{Root}).

Cohesive Zone Traction Distribution using FEA

Three Key Phases:

- Linear Elastic (Rise → Peak traction)
 - Linear Damage/Softening (Peak Traction to Zero Traction)
 - Crack Propagation Phase
- Compressive tractions that occur are always considered elastic (no damage)

The distribution of cohesive tractions along the crack path are exported from FE stress database) and the different phases are shown (right)

Representative Contour plot of traction distribution in FEA

R-curve Traction Laws as FEA inputs

Intrinsically monitoring crack length from the initial separated nodal pair is not a built-in feature of the current software version in LS-DYNA.

However, to demonstrate the influence of the R-curve, the in-plane elements along the crack path were assigned variable traction law properties as measured in the experiments.

- The Model R-curve (experiments) has been discretized in steps of $l_e = 0.508$ mm
- The Bi-linear inputs to the Cohesive Zone Model were fed in based on this step length
- Considered a very high initial stiffness for all traction law properties ($\delta_{elastic} = \frac{\delta_{critical}}{100}$)

Direct Inputs to Model the R-Curve in FEA

Initial Crack Tip

As evident above- at a load line displacement of 6mm, the crack propagation lengths differ in the three different simulations.

This highlights the need for incorporating R-curve response in predictive models for accurate modeling of delamination lengths

Summary & Conclusions

Key Objectives:

- Characterize the fracture toughness of plain weave glass epoxy laminated composite as a key material property
- Developing Inputs for a cohesive zone model using experimentally determined traction laws to predict the extent and spread of delamination

Approach:

- Using a high instrumented DIC (Digital Image Correlation) setup to measure slopes and displacements needed for the determination of fracture toughness and traction laws.
- Fracture Toughness was measured using G (LEFM) J-Integral based approaches for the plain weave glass epoxy material system. Replicate testing showed reasonably good repeatability.

Key Results:

- Classic R-curve response measured, and ensemble model curve has been developed as a function of crack growth.
- Experimentally measured TSLs help generate Bi-linear inputs for FE (MAT 138) to predict crack growth.
- Cohesive zone length measurements using DIC full field measurements help in understanding the material's response (damage in the softening region) and allows for a more realistic representation of deformation the crack tip region.
- Including R-curve in FE (an auto-driven feature currently lacking the state-of-the-art FE software), shows that it is required for accurate prediction of delamination lengths.

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